
EVOLVING BELIEF KNOWLEDGE GRAPHS: AN ACTIVE INFERENCE FRAMEWORK FOR INFORMATION FORAGING IN PARTIALLY OBSERVABLE ENVIRONMENTS *

Andrew B. Pashea
Active Inference Institute
andrewbpashea@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This paper introduces a novel framework for evolving belief knowledge graphs that combines Active Inference principles with modern language models for dynamic information processing and belief updating, where entities and relationships (graph nodes and edges) maintain their observation histories. The system employs large language models as information interpreters within a broader cognitive architecture that includes mechanisms for belief updating, uncertainty tracking, and source attribution. Unlike traditional static knowledge graphs, our framework treats information processing as an active, continuous process of belief formation and updating, similar to human cognitive processes. The architecture maintains transparency through detailed tracking of information sources, confidence measures, and belief histories, while supporting integration with various analytical tools, reasoning mechanisms, database infrastructures, agents, and other graphs. Graphical structures themselves further allow for graph level analytics and visualization, e.g., emergent concept connectedness and communities. The knowledge graph serves as a dynamic model of an agent's understanding of its environment, capturing both epistemic (imprecise data) and aleatoric (true randomness) uncertainty in its representation of the world. The theoretical foundations of this framework are described followed by an outline of its potential applications in information foraging, risk assessment, and dynamic environment modeling.

Keywords Active Inference · Graph Reasoning · Knowledge Graph · Risk Assessment

1 Active Inference Framework and Partial Observability with Partial Evidence

or an agent who observes their stomach growling and other internal (interoceptive) signals might infer that they are hungry.

1.1 Partial observability: beliefs from sense-making

An *agent*, here the abstract general term for an organism, person, robot, or other system with agency, sense-making, and/or decision-making being considered and potentially computationally modeled, is typically considered to be within a partially observable environment. An agent does not necessarily know the reality of its environment and instead, via the generative model (like a *mind* or relational model of how the world works) with which the agent is (equipped), draws from sensory evidence to infer and learn a model of its environment, "beliefs," in real-time. Sensory observations, like visual, auditory, and other stimuli, are used to infer hidden states about the world, e.g., an agent who observes darkness outdoors might infer it is nighttime,

1.2 Belief updating from sense-making

However, neither of these hidden state inferences—likenable to hypotheses regarding the cause of the darkness outdoors—may necessarily be true: a solar eclipse in the former case or a growing stomach ulcer in the latter could be possible without further information but, having the knowledge that they are less likely than nighttime and hunger, the agent might opt for the more likely hypotheses. In computational modeling, the agent's beliefs about competing hypotheses are typically represented by a probability distribution over hidden states, where higher probabilities reflect a more certain hypothesis.

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It might be that prior to observing darkness outdoors, the agent was uncertain about the time, such that their beliefs about day or night were a near-maximally uncertain distribution s_{time} over the hidden states $[day, night]$, or $Cat([0.5, 0.5])$, as the agent did not hear news of an upcoming eclipse and virtually does not expect it while the two primary competing hypotheses of *day* and *night* have equivalent probabilities (0.5 each). After observing it is dark outdoors, taking account of this visual sensory input, the agent might then infer $Cat([0.0, 1.0])$ to denote it is entirely certain that it is indeed *night*.

1.3 Uncertain evidence from uncertain sources

However, the aforementioned agent might receive a message from a friend: "this eclipse is incredible!" and, alarming to our agent, they quickly infer a new distribution $[1.0, 0.0]$ and *day* wins—until later, of course, when *night* approaches or instead, when the friend reveals the message was a prank all along. Our agent might take its level of trust in the friend or their information into consideration. This lends towards an additional layer of partial observability to consider in cases of interpreting information and *how* to understand that information. This can also true for cases of imprecise, distorted, or otherwise faulty sensory receptors, as in the case of a near-sighted person who cannot necessarily trust that the object in the distance is what they might otherwise infer it to be until taking a closer look.

1.4 Minimizing uncertainty: Perception, Action, and Action-Perception Loops

The agent uncertain of the eclipse could question their friend, as could the near-sighted agent take a closer look, to gain more certainty about the situation. This is a key, yet ultimately simple, transition in cognitive and neuroscientific theory as the paradigm has shifted away from viewing living beings as passive observers towards viewing sense-making as information-seeking or goal-driven behavior whereby perception is combined with taking actions necessary to test current beliefs. The "loop" metaphor for this process of observing, inferring, and acting is apt though in realistic settings it should be considered to be continuous, where the complex human organism (among other complex organisms) does all three of these actions simultaneously perpetually, whether it be while reading a message, reflecting on the evidence for the true time of day, to autonomic processes like blood-oxygen regulation for maintaining bodily regulation without much conscious effort.

1.5 Partial Evidence analogy and Distributions for inferring distributions

One legal notion of "partial evidence" is an apt analogy for partial observability: evidence that establishes an isolated or detached fact which, by itself, does not prove the ultimate fact in dispute but may contribute to proving it when connected with other evi-

dence (<https://law.justia.com/codes/guam/title-6/division-2/chapter-1/>). This is an apt analogy for partial observability: the darkness outdoors is a fact (as far as our agent trusts their vision) but is not sufficient to determine that it is *night*, yet it may be treated as partial evidence of the potential primary fact to be determined. A friend's message about an eclipse, our agent might infer, itself might lead to an inference about its trustworthiness or dishonesty $[honest, dishonest]$ represented by our agent's belief distribution s_{trust} as $[0.66, 0.33]$, i.e. the friend's message is generally trustworthy, though the 0.33 allows for the significant probability that it is false information. In this case, when modeling, rather than taking the information as a singular value denoting the existence of the received information (the agent taking the message to be honest without question, nullifying the concern over trust, and directly moving to the inference over s_{time}), there might instead be another process: inferring $s_{trust} = Cat([0.66, 0.33])$ about the message followed by using this belief distribution for a higher-order belief about s_{time} , such that an observation (the message) can itself be represented probabilistically as well, as the honesty or dishonesty of the message could potentially strongly bias the final inference over s_{time} .

2 Knowledge Graphs

2.1 Knowledge Graphs: Connecting entities and relationships

Knowledge graph structures have been an emergent tool for representing knowledge in graphical structures, where nodes (or vertices) \mathcal{G} may represent real-world or conceptual entities, from persons and places to ideas and notions like "sustainable development" or "analytic philosophy"; in the most general sense, a node is typically a noun even if it refers to a particular action, event, adjective, or otherwise, drawing attention to the significance of language and reasoning over entities in a broad sense. Edges \mathcal{V} are then undirected or directed relationships between, and represented as lines connecting, entities in the knowledge graph. Any node or edge may carry various attributions, such as an index or ID for unique tracking, a description (what the node or edge represents in words), quantitative information (e.g., a particular bank account with x savings), a timestamp of its creation in cases of updating, and so on depending upon purpose or use-case.

2.2 Knowledge Graphs for flexible modeling, scalability, and queries

There may be a knowledge graph for a bank, for example, where a node for a particular customer contains attributes or metadata like the customer's name, address, and date of account creation, while a directed edge with the description "is advised by", with attributes like "Relationship Start Date" or "Relationship Termination Date" or "Customer Feedback", might be drawn from the customer to a node representing a particular financial advisor staff

member of the bank. The result is a graphical model of a real-world scenario which could be applied to the bank's entire customer base, producing a full representation of customer accounts relationships. The knowledge graph maintains flexible scalability as it is not restricted to (but can be converted into) matrix/tabular or tensor (greater than 2-dimensional matrix) structures as are frequently used in the cases of spreadsheet record-keeping and SQL tables, as well as in matrix or tensor operations used in Active Inference and other frameworks involving belief-updating procedures in discrete state space settings.

The attributes or metadata of a particular node or edge are also, in principle, expandable (subject to hardware or computational requirements at high volumes, as with any other storage or operational consideration) such that very unique pieces of information can be stored in a single node or edge rather than requiring expanding entire columns (or dimensions) in a spreadsheet-like structure. A knowledge graph may be stored easily in familiar formats, such as Python 'dict' objects and JSON format and files, rendering them query-able in a way similar to querying unstructured database which can be made dependable when norms are applied, e.g., every customer having a "Account Type" and "Account Creation Date" attribute allows for querying these attributes like fields in any other database; or assigning customer types with their own unique fields, where the knowledge graph can filter to a particular type of customer followed by accessing that type's unique fields. This allows for structured querying, as in the case of Google's knowledge graph logic when querying an entity about whom much knowledge is known and stored online such as querying a major city to see a sidebar denoting the name, country, population size, and various other attributes of the city (.). Terms like "dynamic" or "evolving" are often used to describe the scenario where a knowledge graph is expected to change information and/or structure, as in the case of the bank adding more accounts and tracking creation dates (more nodes and edges) or in Google gathering and updating unique attributes about an entity which other entities do not share, e.g., the population of a country updated from the latest census report or the Milky Way Galaxy as a node which might contain the attribute "Constellations" with a list of constellations, an attribute containing sub-attributes none of which virtually all other nodes or edges share (noting their are likely nodes representing each constellation, thus implying a node-attribute mapping which could call for a new edge, etc., or collecting attributes into a node based on its edges for summary purposes). A knowledge graph could then, in principle, be used to build an approximate or holistic (dependent upon framing and data availability) model of an entire customer relations environment, or a city as an environment, cellular phenomena, an engineered system with actuators for undertaking tasks with reactivity to incoming data, or many organisms and their environment with pre-specified or dynamic relationships between them.

2.3 Graph Analytics

As a tool for analysis and modeling, graph structures offer network measures like node degree, the PageRank algorithm, bridging coefficients, interactive inspection and visualization (particularly interpretable when nodes and/or edges contain their labels or names, definitions, attributes, and visual connections to other nodes), and other metrics for inspecting the graph itself, which is especially relevant to graphs whose information changes and updates based on changes in the environment it attempts to model. These metrics allow for finding nodes most essential to the current structure, such as those with exponentially higher numbers of relationships with other nodes than others; recognizing emergent communities or cliques of nodes whose connections are most numerous with one another locally with sparse, if any, connections to the rest of the graph; and nodes which act as key connecting nodes that form a relationships between otherwise disparate nodes, acting as bridges which form a singular or sparse connection between two large populations.

These metrics can be employed alongside other measures in cases of quantitative data stored in nodes or edges, as in the case of bank account balances, posts or connections between social media user networks, or more generally any scenario where multiple nodes and/or edges in a graph are considered to represent random variables whose values are realized at different points in time, adding a temporal layer to the graphical model where one can infer statistical, probabilistic, and/or causal relationships among variables. One can simultaneously monitor how a system "moves" as node connectivity, statistical patterns between communities of nodes, sizes of nodes (figuratively when carrying quantitative data as attributes, or more literally where node sizes can be indexed to the numeric data and visualized).

2.4 AI Integrations

Automated knowledge-graph composition via natural language processing tools for computational encoding or "reading" of human-produced text, e.g., in documents websites, etc. like Named Entity Recognition for identity key concepts or entities, topic modeling and embedding transformers for semantic similarity categorization and similarity, relational machine learning and graph neural networks for working with unstructured, combinatorial, or graphical data, and more recently large language models (LLMs) whose increasingly exhibited complex reasoning performance and accuracy brought interest in using them for aspects of reasoning over natural language text. For example, LLMs have been employed for foraging information from databases, internet search, or a large corpus of text for knowledge graph "discovery" in the sense of making sense of large amounts of text which might otherwise, say, take a research team a lifetime to coherently interpret, categorize, measure, in addition to drawing out patterns and relationships between entities.

3 Evolving Knowledge Graphs in Real-Time Partially-Observable Environments with Partial Evidence

3.1 Modeling

This paper proposes an evolving knowledge graph structure informed by principles from Active Inference as a conceptual base unit for a particular agentic architecture in an information-foraging paradigm. This refers to knowledge graphs whose nodes, edges, and respective attributes are added, removed, connected, or otherwise updated and which operate in relation to or interact with interfaces beyond itself. This paper focuses upon an initial simpler variant for illustration, where a knowledge graph can be related to a statistical or Bayesian network, Markov random field, or other general form of model of variables with probabilistic or dynamically updated relationships.

As we earlier considered perception in Active Inference as sense-making for belief inference and action selection, with partial observability and potentially partial evidence and measures of uncertainty, this variant conceives of LLMs not simply to scan but rather "read" documents via chunking information—empirically found to typically offer richer and more input-referential information than summarizing large amounts of text or entire documents within individual calls—sequentially as in a perception loop where the LLM receives partial information, extracts nodes (concepts) and edges (relationships between concepts), and itself infers the best knowledge representation for this information.

The "partial evidence" metaphor applies as the proposed design maintains the framework of beliefs and trustworthiness of information or source of information: extracted nodes and edges from each sequential chunk of information are timestamped with their respective creation (or "observation") time, source (e.g., document, site, database, an agent), and chunk of text (for direct traceback). The reading perception loop proceeds via extract nodes and edges with their respective textual descriptions as well as a probability value expressing the LLM's inferred self-reported measure of confidence in its representation. As nodes and edges are read in sequentially, in case of incoming duplicate nodes or edges (calling for an 'update'), the next incoming node is merged with the previous node, thus concatenating their respective observation timestamps, descriptions, and probability values into a single node containing histories of these attributes in lists. This is essentially a historical knowledge graph fit to a paradigm for real-time operations for dynamic environments, adaptive to paradigmatic or volatile shifts in environmental data while maintaining the transparency of labeled, described nodes, edges, and attributes. Probability values across nodes maintain a trackable parameter for their confidence in the information, as well as an inferred hidden state as piece of original texted is transformed into a description, thus an evolving "belief" knowledge graph.

This kind of paradigm and base unit formulation lends towards a variety of tool integrations. From the perspective of Active Inference, such models might be parameterized as approximate models of their environment where update and free energy minimization rules may apply. This may be paired with other interesting model architectures and data compression or transformation layers; multimodal data integration in structured yet flexible graph models of environmental variables, e.g., real-time incoming or changing numeric- or discrete-valued data; relational machine or deep learning networks, or continuous, discrete, or hybrid Active Inference models for optimization and modulation of variables and graph structures; cognition and reasoning or reflection mechanisms for using reasoning to make further connections between existing nodes and edges via reasoning, a goal prompt, or search APIs for finding permissible internet sources; pruning and reconsolidation mechanisms for managing memory, e.g., model or structure learning for finding the optimal minimal amount of information necessary to holistically represent current information; hypothesis generation and testing for addressing less certain regions of the graph or recognizing conflicting information and using the traced probabilistic concepts and relationships for addressing the uncertainty; action or policy actuators for acting on information received via trigger or preemptive planning mechanisms; relating or judging information based on other common natural language measures like finding cosine similarity or named entity recognition between text chunks as filtering mechanisms or for computing potential information gain (finding rich or novel information prior to LLM prompting); short-term memory or probabilistic RAG operations where multiple recent or more probabilistic node-edge paths in the graph can be concatenated to add more context for deeper prompting; precision parameters, learning rates, or free energy minimization for inferring global confidence scores for an entire node or edge or reconsolidating nodes and edges with larger multi-document summaries as rich hypotheses stored in single nodes and edges; chain-of-thought and other dynamic prompt-response logics for deeper reasoning; multi-agent frameworks for both individual inference (individual belief graphs per agent) or federated inference (shared belief graphs) and further agentic workflows for optimizing, tracking, and supporting via graph retrieval augmented generation the LLM's thought processes in a model based in natural language and interpretable variables; and belief graph summaries with higher context window LLMs for full natural language reporting of results.

The perspective of LLMs and natural language processors capable of reasoning is crucial to this design: though a central design component, the LLM alone is not the "agent." Instead, it is the broader architecture including the sense-making and belief formation of the graph as a kind of memory storage, management, and updating system for what would otherwise be an amnesic LLM once its context window is surpassed. The training and retraining of LLMs is not only costly but disallows tracking the particu-

Figure 1: Knowledge Graph Paths: From reading a single document regarding nature-based financial and policy decision-making, with the goal prior "Find reliable information to inform a sustainable business plan" which biases the attention of the LLM to seek information it deems potentially relevant and draw connections. This results in *Sustainable Business Plan* appearing most frequently in the sequential observation graph extractions both as an individual node and with edge connections to other nodes. This prepares for future iterations, analysis, and hypothesis generation and testing with *Sustainable Business Plan* as the center of gravity, e.g., testing and/or enriching the connections and definitions with further reading and/or reasoning mechanisms.

lar text sources most guiding a prompted response, losing transparency and accountability in application. The evolving knowledge graph as a base unit for the system design remedies these issues by allowing an agent architecture which can gather, consolidate, and retrieve information in a principled way beyond an LLM-only approach.

The "beliefs" framing further accounts for partially observable environments, as having means of tracking uncertainty while maintaining a healthy skepticism toward full reliance upon LLMs: as LLMs are increasingly being considered for full production, analytics, and enterprise settings, transparency of agentic processes and the ability to reason and communicate (or "translate") computational results in natural language for stakeholders unfamiliar with computer programming or NLP will be key for organizational collaboration and trust. Augmenting agentic work-

flows with cognitive science-inspired principles and processes, where LLMs function as information interpreters with trust dynamics, then produces an interpretable long-term memory system ready for integration with other tools and memory mechanisms for prioritizing, weighting, and resolving conflicts between information which requires more tact than raw prompts to LLMs. In dealing with natural language where words, signifiers, syllogisms, predicates, and the various complexities and multidimensional linguistics of language—and how humans actually acquire and then reason with language in multitudes of ways—all require reasoning and bearing with uncertain contexts and definitions of information via iterative observation, evaluation, and hypothesis generation and testing, rather than hastily assuming an LLM and its source information are precise.

4 Information-Foraging Paradigm

Now focusing on the simpler variant system at hand, we begin with a single document from which our "agent" (the LLM in combination with the broader architecture) will infer and consolidate its beliefs. The general outline is as follows:

- **Text-chunking into individuals "observations":** The document is chunked via a recursive character text splitter. As an example setting, a text string (e.g., an encoded document) can be split into chunks of roughly 500 characters with 150 character overlaps between chunks to maintain overlapping information between chunks.
- **Source tracking:** A string containing the source from which the chunks were produced is ap-

pended to a dict containing all of the chunks, tracking the source information.

- **"Goal Prior"** A non-essential step, prior to node and edge attraction, is to define a *goal prior* which aligns with the notions of preferences and self-evidencing in Active Inference. It is essentially a string containing a directive relative to a goal, for example "Look for credible information about X" which is then formatted into the prompt to the LLM for extracting nodes and edges. This explicitly directs the LLM's attention towards goal-relevant information. This goal prior can either be statically set for all operations or dynamic as the flexibility of this overall agentic system allows for revising goals or pre-specifying goals depending on the operation at hand. This also provides front-end users with the ability to direct operations towards goals as opposed to purely relying on the LLM to simply "extract nodes and edges" without further detail (unless desired).
- *Preliminary results of this approach find that LLMs are dramatically more likely to extract information relevant to this goal prior, e.g., finding and discovering connections between X from a document which implies useful information for this goal but is not itself dedicated to the topic. This can be combined with graph RAG for information as well, e.g., "Look for credible information about X. This is what we know thus far: {formatted high-probability beliefs about X}". This graph RAG option will likely provide more context and pre-established probabilistic/evidential facts to the LLM, diminishing hallucination risks.*
- **Loop for observations to inferred observation graphs:** A perception loop is carried out whereby an LLM is prompted to return JSON-formatted key concepts and relationships, with descriptions and probability values as confidence measures. This produces a potentially long series of relatively small prompt-response iterations as the LLM "observes" the text chunks sequentially and produces the confidence-weighted node and edge representations. The final graph extracted per iteration is then stamped with metadata, e.g., timestamp, source document citation, source observation chunk for traceback to the actual text from which the nodes and edges were extracted. Each extracted graph from a chunk observation can then itself be considered to be a small "observation graph" (as it is traceable to an individual text observation), containing an inferred representation of the observation.
- These various small observation graphs are then consolidated where update rules are applied. In this variant, nodes are simply merged such that the 'description' metadata field instead becomes a list of description histories; this same logic is carried out for 'timestamp', 'source document', 'source observation', 'probability history' and other metadata.
- Because the observations are processed *sequentially*—akin to a human reading a document from start to finish, updating their understanding of the document and noticing potentially conflicting or uncertain information (e.g., unclear definitions, seeking information with a goal in mind and parsing their understanding of the text in relation to this goal)—the first observation graph becomes the "prior" as in a Bayesian belief updating scheme where new observations (contiguously read chunks) are then used to update the overall belief about the concept or relationship represented by node or edge *i*.
- In addition to the probability value history of each individual observation graph, there is also a probability representative of the entire node or edge, for example receiving 10 different observation graphs all of which contain a common concept and consolidating these nodes into a single node containing 10 distinct observations, probabilities, and potentially distinct source documents with an overview probability representing this consolidation. For cognitive realism, instead of simply averaging probabilities, we can apply Bayesian or free energy minimizing update rules, as well as other common metrics for natural language measurement like semantic and cosine similarity between incoming and prior beliefs, by treating the first observation graph as a prior. In another setting, another approach could be to assume 0.5 as a prior representing complete uncertainty—the concept had never been observed before—followed by updating based on incoming observations.
- **Visualization and Graph Analytics**

Note Special note

5 Data Availability Statement

GitHub code under development.

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